

PROTECTING MINORITIES IN EUROPEAN COVENANTS AND CHARTERS (CHALLENGES FOR THE STATE OF ISRAEL)

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Abstract: *The establishment of the United Nations organization brought an approach by which private human rights and the non-discrimination principle are sufficient means to protect all individuals including minority group members. The fact that minority groups in the population are discriminated was not a sufficient ground for collective rights for such minority. Historical, political, or national policy reasons regarding immigration and assimilation in various countries strengthen the alienation approach towards this group dimension. This article will seek to review several known covenants from the European Council that concerns for minority groups all over the continent.*

Key words: *United Nations; Civil and Political Rights; European Union.*

PROTECȚIA MINORITĂȚILOR ÎN CONVENȚELE ȘI CARTE EUROPENE (PROVOCĂRI PENTRU STATUL ISRAEL)

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Rezumat: *Înființarea Organizației Națiunilor Unite a adus o abordare prin care drepturile private ale omului și principiul nediscriminării sunt mijloace suficiente pentru a proteja toți indivizii, inclusiv membrii grupurilor minoritare. Faptul că grupurile minoritare din populație sunt discriminate nu a fost un motiv suficient pentru drepturile colective pentru o astfel de minoritate. Motivele istorice, politice sau de politică națională privind imigrația și asimilarea în diferite țări întăresc abordarea alienării față de această dimensiune a grupului. Acest articol va încerca să studieze mai multe convenții cunoscute din partea Consiliului European care se referă la grupurile minoritare de pe tot continentul.*

Cuvinte cheie: *Națiunile Unite; drepturi civile și politice; Uniunea Europeană.*

1. Introduction

The establishment of the United Nations organization brought an approach by which private human rights and the non-discrimination principle are sufficient means to protect all individuals including minority group members. The fact that minority groups in the population are discriminated was not a sufficient ground for collective rights for such minority. Historical, political, or national policy reasons regarding immigration and assimilation in various countries strengthen the alienation approach towards this group dimension. According to Cullen [7], the two main human rights covenants are the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights – ICCPR and the International Covenant on Social, Economic and Cultural Rights – ICSECR. Koch [10] adds that it was adopted in 1967 and validated in 1976. These covenants were reconfirmed by the Israeli government in 1992. It should be mentioned that the two covenants open with identical section that emphasizes people's right for self-definition. Although self-definition here is on the context of nations fight for liberation from colonialism. National minorities in nation countries are not recognized. There are several covenants in the European Union council that establish the treatment of authorities to the minority groups.

2. Main Materials

Currently, the rights of national minority groups are not a separate and unique part in the European Union legislation, and those who are part of national minorities have the same rights as any other citizen in the European Union [7, 135 p.]. The countries who are member of the European Union are obligated to apply non-discrimination principles for all citizens regardless their belonging to national minority groups and provide them all the rights the Union citizens are entitled to. However, Ahrens & Woodward [1] indicates that in some cases the European Union has enshrined in legislation concrete rights of certain minorities. The European Union has already set in 1993 the demand that every joining country should guarantee minority protection and respecting their rights as acceptance criterion. Buyse [6] seeks to emphasize that the **Council of Ministers of the European Union** has published a statement by which countries who ask for the Union financial aid has to respect human rights and minority rights. Moreover, according to the same statement, the Union will negotiate for signing international covenants with other countries only if the latter show a genuine commitment to recognition of human rights and minority rights. The **Council of Ministers** defines this commitment through three criteria the country must show: recognition of minority right to establish and have education, culture and religion organizations or institutes; provide minorities a proper opportunity to use their language in courts

and public authorities; providing sufficient protection to refugees and displaced persons when returning to areas where they were ethnic minority. The European Union also applies requirements regarding minorities to its member countries, for example, all union member countries are obligated to provide minorities basic rights, including freedom of association, freedom of movement, discrimination prohibition and the right to vote and be elected to European Union institutes [8]. as noted, different covenants that allow cultural empowerment of minorities were written and distribute among the European Union countries. herein several examples.

European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR). According to Shepherd [14], this convention was phrased by the European council in 1950 and its subject was European covenant for human rights. Emirbayer & Goldberg [8] notes that all the countries who are member of the European council signed it. Salgado [13] emphasizes that this covenant determines basic rights for people in Europe. A person who believes his rights have been violated by a country that has signed this convention, can address the European Court of Human Rights. It should be mentioned that over the years several protocols were added to the convention and enshrined additional rights or extended existing rights. Unanimous consensus of all member countries was required to validate additional protocol. While in cases of extending existing rights, each country had to sign and reconfirm the extension. It should be cleared that the convention does not specifically refer minorities, moreover, the convention does not define what is a national minority.

However, recommendation made in 1993, about adding a protocol in the subject of national minority rights, the parliament assembly offered to adopt national minority definition as "*a group of people living in a country, who live in their territory and they are its citizens; who keep strong and long term connections with this country; who have ethnical, cultural, religious or lingual unique characteristics; have significant representation in the country population, even if their rate is smaller comparing to other population in the country or region; they have motivation to preserve together the characteristics that have created their unique identity, including their culture, tradition, religion of language*" [1, 491 p.]. As noted, this recommendation was not applied eventually, and the offered protocol is not part of the convention.

Section 9 in the convention enshrine the freedom of religion and **provides national minority groups the right to freely realize they faith.** **Section 10** in the convention enshrine the **freedom of speech**, and as a result of it national minority groups have the right to use their language privately or among the group members. The practical meaning of **this right also includes the right to publish newspaper**

or any other media in their language without the state intervention. It should be clear that the convention applies for private people and there is no collective protection for minority groups or general protection. **Section 14** determines discrimination prohibition on base of gender, race, color, language or religion. Section 23 sets the right to use the minority language, political opinion or other, national or social source, property, place of birth or belonging to national minority. Usually, this section is not separate but joins violation of another right protected by the convention. If a person was discriminated, he may stand for his rights in the European human rights court. Additional convention that adds political – cultural legitimacy to the cultural space in Europe is the minority framework convention.

The Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities (FCNM) was phrased on November 10th, 1994, and was validated in the European council and adopted by the European Council of Ministers on February 1st, 1998. Only 39 of the countries who are council members have signed this convention, and some of it did it with reservations. The framework convention is considered an important tool that sets basic standards for minority protection. Moreover, the convention is considered to be the first of its kind in the member countries of the Council of Europe and the European Union of creating legal principles countries can adopt to ensure national minority protection, **and for many it is the most important and binding legal document for minority protection** [2].

The framework convention mainly includes directions that determine goals the countries must set rather than the steps to be taken to fulfil these goals, those are kept being considered by the states in their internal legislation. The framework convention **does not** include the "**national minority**" definition because there is no wide agreement about it among the European council members. The framework convention comprised of **five chapters**. The **third** chapter includes principles for interpreting the convention sections. For example, section 21 determines that the convention should not be interpreted in a way that provides the right to act in a way that will risk a state's territorial integrity [11]. The **fourth and fifth** chapters set the principles by which the European Council of Ministers will engage supervision mechanisms on the convention implementation, and subjects related to joining the convention. However, the **first** chapter sets some general principles, the first and most important is that protecting national minority rights is part of protecting human rights [9]. In addition, it emphasizes that every person who is part on a national minority has the right to choose if he wants to be treated as a member of this minority or not. The **second** chapter, which central in the framework convention, includes the basic principles states have to cat by and enshrine in their internal legislation. These principles deal with many subjects as detailed:

- **Prohibition of discrimination** - states must ensure that national minority group members are not discriminated because of being part of this group. Moreover, the convention determines that states have to act to promote **effective equality** between national minority group members and the majority group.

- **Taking steps to ensure development of the unique identity and culture** of national minorities.

- **Encouraging tolerance, dialogue, mutual respect** and understanding among all the country residents.

- **Defending the rights** of national minority groups to gather, unite, and defend freedom of expression, thought, conscience and religion of these groups' members.

- **Ensuring approach** to media and encouraging national minority groups to establish and use media.

- Acknowledging national minorities right to **use their language in private or in public**, and present information in the minority group language.

- **Official acknowledgement of private and family names** of national minority group members.

- Acknowledging minority group members right to **use their language in managerial authorities** and adopt in local legislation the obligation to use bilingual road signage (in the majority language and in the minority language).

- **Promoting knowledge about the culture, history, language and religion** of the majority and the minority groups.

- Acknowledging minority group right to establish and independently manage **their education institutes and teach the next generations**.

Organization for Security and Cooperation (OSCE) is comprised of 57 countries in Europe, Central Asia and North America. The organization engages with political, **security, economic, environmental and humanitarian** subjects. according to Ghana & Rahmani [9] it also deals with **human rights, democratization and national minorities**. The organization decision is based on general agreement of the member countries, but it has no binding legal validity. The countries who are member of the organization are **committed to enable equal rights to all people to participate the economic, social, and political life**. Defending minorities is perceived by the organization as part of proper governance and social integration promotion [10]. Moreover, the organization promotes the perception that resolving conflicts with ethnic minorities is in the highest interest of the state and its majority group because, when minorities see their rights are kept and they can participate the local politics and influence it, they may support the country they live in. the organization also operates local programs that focus on

defending ethnic minorities, education system reforms, increasing proper representation for minority members, increasing minority language use, reducing discrimination, establishing community institutes for minorities and protecting their rights. The organization has High Commissioner of National Minorities (HCNM), whose role is to interfere in situations he believes have political tension that is related to national minority, which may develop into a conflict. In addition, the commissioner analyses short term and long-term factors that lead to ethnic tensions and advises the member countries how to cope with these situations.

It will be noted that at the conference in Copenhagen in 1990 the Conference on Security and Cooperation in Europe (CSCE) has adopted a document, that despite having no legal binding, it has great political importance as significant step to promote the recognition of minority group rights. The document has determined **that minority group members are entitled to establish their institutes, the state must maintain their unique identity and that the minority language has to be taught in public schools. In addition, the document determined that minority group members must be allowed to participate the state public life**, and it was also noted that one way to fulfil these goals is by providing autonomy to the minorities. The document has also emphasized the duty of the minority group members to respect the territorial integrity of the country they live in.

The status in Israel. According to Barak -Erez [2], currently, minority members, Israeli citizens, are being discriminated almost in all life areas – in occupation, government resources allocation for education, and in housing, land and planning – and they are excluded from most decision-making centers. Racist attitudes and practices are also increased in the last years. The civil rights association fights minority members discrimination with legal, public and educational means. **In education** – which is the real key for more egalitarian and just future – there are huge gaps between the Jewish population and the minority groups. these are expressed among other things in shortage in classrooms that causes high overcrowding, and severe shortage of professionals, as regular visiting officers, educational counselors, and educational psychologists [3]. The obligation **to proper representation of minority members, according to existing conventions**, in the state institutes and in the public service is driven from minority members legal right to equality. According to this obligation, the government and all those with authority to appoint representatives in public bodies to ensure minority members adequate representation in these bodies. As for the Bedouin society, there is a many years' problem of **regulating the unacknowledged villages**. There is a conflict between the Bedouins and the state in two aspects:

acknowledgement of historical villages and property rights recognition in the land. On both issues the state attitude toward the Bedouin Arab citizens in the Negev is forceful and accompanied by public atmosphere of de-legitimization of their claims and rights. The land and planning is one of the areas where the minority members in Israel are subject to sever deprivation and discrimination. Since there is no proper housing solutions and no infrastructure planning that enable legal building in the Arab settlements, the residents have to build illegally. Although the state is responsible for this situation, the house destruction policy continues in the Arab settlements and in the mixed cities.

3. Conclusions

The article editor concludes that collective rights are provided to ethnical minority group or an individual of this group by the state. The state determines the scope and institutional support of these rights, which are aimed to maintain the unique identity of this group and allow its expression and its culture development and preservation. It includes the right for language, education, representation, keeping religious obligations and freedom of worship. According to the article editor opinion and various conventions of the European Union, and comparing to the State of Israel, there are several approaches to minority rights: (1) extreme liberal approach – the group as a group has no rights, only individuals have rights. The state will prohibit any group organization. (2) moderate liberal approach – groups are acknowledged, but the state will not assist these groups. (3) approach that acknowledges group rights – the state acknowledges the groups and even assist them to preserve their uniqueness as expressed in the European conventions.

There is no doubt that Israel is part of "deeply divided societies" category because it has minorities that are more than 20% of the population and there are many differences between the Jewish majority and the minorities that are dividing in language, culture, religion, nationality, and ideology. These differences are added, as noted, to long history of hostility and violence. The Arab society in Israel, which is the minority society, is living besides the contradiction between the Jewish Zionist nature of the State of Israel and its democratic values. The Arabs are aware to the fact that although they are the state citizens, they unfortunately feel that they will never have full and equal rights.

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